

MADHESH UNIVERSITY

INTRODUCTION

Madhesh University (MU), established on Bhadra 23, 2079 B.S., is a beacon of higher education in the Madhesh Province, dedicated to nurturing skilled manpower and fostering the all-round development of the nation. Rooted in the belief that quality education is the cornerstone of progress, the university plan to offer a diverse range of courses in art, science, medicine, tourism, Ayurveda, law, management, education, oriental philosophy, technical fields, and various other subjects.

The establishment of MU was driven by the vision to create an educational and academic environment that is characterized by excellence, integrity, and productivity. The provincial assembly of Madhesh Province enshrined this vision into reality through the formulation of an Madhesh University Act, which allowed for the establishment and operation of the university. The province's gazette, on Baisekh 14, 2079, MU embarked on its journey to shape the future of countless students and contribute significantly to the progress and development of the nation.

With a profound commitment to competition-based education and the concept of a university, MU is dedicated to continuously raising the bar in higher education standards. As the university takes first steps towards its mission, it seeks to create an educational ecosystem that is learner-centric. It strives to be at the forefront of higher education institutions in the region.

MU is the founding member of the Regional Centre of Expertise (RCE) for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) established in 2023 in Nepal. The RCE has been initiated globally by the University of United Nations, Institute for the Advanced Study of Sustainability, Japan. With this affiliation MU has from very beginning conceptualized the environment sensitivity with less carbon emission as envisioned by Nepal Government. It aims to focus on life-skill and sustained livelihood based courses through culture-friendly pedagogy. Thus, MU is a unique university with special features to intervene in higher education incorporated by the Province Government of Madhesh. It undertakes the culture-friendly pedagogy and very specific but open courses for life-skill and quality of livelihood development.

VISION

Creating an image of the University as a centre of excellence for higher education, research and innovation focusing on quality education, skills development, industry integration and holistic eco-system for global competencies among the youth and sustainable development of the Nation.

MISSION

To advance and expand knowledge of various academic streams through teaching and research for academic excellence and collaboration with diverse institutions for accessible, affordable, high-quality education.

GOAL

Apply the modest learning technologies and pedagogies for developing the university 'centre of academic excellence' through delivering high-quality academic programs.

OBJECTIVES

- Conduct various teaching, training and research programs as prescribed for the development of higher education, manage departments and research centers and to supervise and inspect the same.
- Certify the degree to the students, trainees or researchers who have obtained higher education from the University and to award honorary degrees to specific individuals.
- Establish relationships with national and international universities or educational institutions.
- Receive financial support from national and international educational and other institutions and individuals and hold educational exchange programs in accordance with prevailing laws.
- Make necessary arrangement to award prize, scholarship and fellowships.
- Arrange and conduct various sports and welfare programs in the university.
- Certify the student, trainee and researcher who obtain degree from the constituent and affiliated campus of the University and also award honorary degree to special individual.
- Grant approval and affiliation to campuses (colleges) for the academic courses and determine the facilities and support provided by the university to the affiliated campuses (colleges).
- Formulate rules and regulations as may be necessary for the University.
- Execute other necessary work for the betterment of the University and education system.

CORE VALUES

1. **Academic Freedom:** The University Focuses on establishing an academic culture that encourages to the free exchange of ideas in a suitable environment including academic freedom in thinking, creating and expanding knowledge through research, teaching and outreach.

2. **Adaptive:** The University promises responsibly to environment induced changes. A careful monitoring measures over the changes as a result of advancement in technology, research & development and innovation are supposed to be instrumental as to go in changing scenario.

3. **Culture of Excellence:** The University believes on culture of excellence in teaching learning process, research and extension services and extension services as milestones to develop centre of excellence.

4. **Good Governance:** The University believes in accountability, responsiveness, efficiency and effectiveness, rule of law and good governance principles in the process of making and implementation of decisions.

5. **Holistic Approach:** The University believes on holistic education approach commensurate with social, cultural, economic and environmental realities.

6. **Industry Integration:** The University makes every effort to bridge the Gaps between theory and

practice with a focus on skill development and industry integration.

7. Integration: The University is committed to combining individual needs and organizational goals in mutually regarding work environment, ‘gaining’ more humanistic values at the expense of ‘efficiency’.

8. Quality Education: The primary thrust of the university is promoting and expanding quality education through the application of modest learning technologies and pedagogies and delivering high-quality standard education at different levels.

9. Social Justice: The University considers all aspects of the principles of social and equitable justice.

10. Teamwork: Gain synergy in actual work, performance, result and outcome the university is committed to carrying out duties and responsibilities based on a spirit of team management.

GUIDING PRINCIPLE FOR COURSE DESIGN

The following principles have been curated from current research and scholarship about effective blended course design. It is meant to be shared, used and adapted based on the specific needs of local and international contexts.

- Compatible with national/international market
- Based on contemporary issues related with the subject
- In line with the practices of federalism
- Student-centered collaborative learning
- Build upon existing knowledge
- Multiple modes of engagement
- Blending with ethics, integrity and social responsibility
- Grassroots (People)- oriented
- Diversity/Intercultural perspectives
- Practical application
- Connecting learning outcomes to activities and assessments

Many of these principles transcend learning modalities and can be applied in face-to-face, blended, and online learning contexts. Therefore, we have incorporated practical examples for different contexts. The implementation of these principles will vary by modality and discipline and may be broadly useful in decision- making related to the design and delivery of high-quality blended courses.

To develop the course of BA LLB, the subject committee for law has been formulated in the convenorship of Prof. Dr. Yubraj Sangraula, the former Attorney General of Nepal constituting law practitioner and specialists. Likewise, to develop the course on BPAM, the course formulation committee has been formed in the convenorship of the Dean, Dr, Man Bahadur Bk, constituting the officials from Kathmandu University, Nepal Administrative Staff College and other relevant intuitions.

BA LLB Course structures

Approved by the Academic Council dated August 29, 2023 (2080 Bhadra 12)

This course is based on a professional structure, implying that the fundamental objective of the course is to produce legal professionals. The course balances both theoretical and practical necessities. While several subjects, such as legal writing, procedural law, interpretation, evidence law and forensics, represent practical courses, clinical courses have been introduced to teach students skills and arts to apply the law to actual problems.

The course structure also balances between 'applicable law and jurisprudence, the Western and Eastern legal understanding, fundamental and specialized subjects, and core and emerging areas of the profession. Legal education must comprise scientific and logical knowledge, either. Hence, philosophy, logic and science have been included as needed.

Nepal has entered a federal structure. Hence, there are laws made by different government layers. Nepal's specific needs are essential. Therefore, importance is offered to the study of the Constitution, constitutionalism and legislative studies. The structure of the course is designed by the subject committee and experts' groups considering the provisions of the Nepal Bar Council. The course structure contains broader outlines so that the faculty with group of the experts will prepare the course details.

Eligibility: +2 with at least 50 percent mark or C⁺ CGPA in any discipline.

Semester I

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Jr. 100/01	Basic Principles of Law—Jurisprudence, Part 1	1.5
2.	Jr. 100/02	Basic Concepts of Law—Jurisprudence, Part 2	1.5
3.	Sc.200/01	Political Theories and Thoughts: Part-1	1.5.
4.	Sc.200/02	Fundamental Economics: Part-1	1.5
	Sc.200/03	Sociology: Part-1	3
5.	Sc.200/04	Fundamental Management: Part - 1	1.5
6.	Cli.900/01	Clinical Course: Observation of Justice Institutions and Report Writing: Practical, Part-1	3.0
7.	Sc. 200/05	Legal History of Nepal: Part-1	1.5
8.	Lg. 300/01	Legal Nepali: Part-1	3
Total	Eight Subjects	Credits	18

Semester 2

1.	Sc.200/06	Political Theories and Thoughts: Part-II	3.0
2	Jr. 100/03	Theories of Logic	3.0
3.	Sc.200/07	Fundamental Economics: Part-II	1.5
4.	Jr.100/04	Sociology of Law.	3.0
5.	Sc. 200/08	Legal History of Nepal-Part-II	1.5
6.	Sc.200/09	Fundamental Management – Part-II	1.5
7.	Lg.300/02	Legal Nepali-Part II	1.5
8.	CL.300/02	Clinical Law: Research of the Law Enforcement Situation	3.0
Total	8	Credits	18

3rd Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Jr. 100/05	Legislative Principles: Part -I	1.5.
2.	Lg. 300/03	Legal English: Part-I	3.0
3.	Sc.200/10	Nepali Sociology	3.0
4.	CrI.400/01	Criminal Law: Part-I	3.0
5	Intl.500/01	International Relation and Diplomacy: Part-I	3.0
6.	Intl.500/02	Introduction to the Public International Law: Part-I	3.0
7.	Prl. 600/01	Procedural Law: Part-I	3.0
8.	Cl.300/03	Clinical: Visit to Jail and preparation of the report on sentencing system and reform	3.0
		Total credit hour	22.5

4th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Jr. 100/06	Legislative Principles: Part-II	1.5
2.	Lg.300/04	Legal English: Part-II	3
3.	CrI.400/02	Criminal Law: Part-II	3
4.	Intl.500/03	International Relation and Diplomacy: Part-II	3
5.	Intl.500/04	International Law Part-II	1.5
6.	Prl.600/02	Procedural Law: Part-II	1.5
7.	Jr.100/07	Industrial Jurisprudence	1.5
		Total credit hour	15.0

5th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Hr.700/01	International Human Rights Law-Part-I (Civil and Political)	3
2.	Intl.500/05	International Law on Sea, Trade, and Communication	3
3.	Jr. 100/05	Interpretation of Law: Part-II	3
4.	Lr.800/01	Introduction Research Methodology: Part-I	1.5
5.	Cn. 900/01	Introduction to the Constitutional Law: Part I	3
6.	Jr.100/06	Professional Ethics-	3
7.	Prl.600/03	Legal Writing, Civil Case	1.5
8.	Cl.300/03	Clinical: Community (outreach) Service,	1.5
		Total credits	19.5

6th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Hr.700/02	International Human Rights Law:Part – II (Economic, Social and Cultural)	3
2.	Intl.500/06	Public International Law: Part-III (UN Charter and International Peace and Dispute Settlement)	1.5.

3.	Jr.100/07	Evidence Law	3
4.	Lr.800/02	Legal Research: Part-II	1.5
5.	Cn 900/02	Constitutional Law and Constitutionalism: Part-II	3
6.	Jr.100/08	Comparative Jurisprudence	1.5
7.	CrI.400/03	International Criminal Law and Justice	1.5
8.	Cl.300/04	Clinical: Legal Drafting-Criminal	3.0
		Total credit	18.0

7th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Jr. 100/09	Development Jurisprudence	1.5
2.	Cmrl.1000/01	Company Law	1.5
3.	Cmrl.1000/02	Contract Law	1.5
4.	Cn.900/02	Public Administrative Law	1.5
5.	Cl.300/05	Clinical: Mobile Legal Aid and Social Justice Advocacy Service	1.5
6	Cl. 300/06	Legal writing: Commercial Cases	1.5
1.	CrI. 400/04	Forensic Evidence	3.0
2.	CrI.400/05	Criminology	3.0
1.	Cmrl.1000/04	Banking/Financial Law	3.0
2.	Cmrl.1000/05	International Trade Law	3.0
1.	Cn.900/03	Laws on Good Governance	3.0
2.	Cn.900/04	Electoral Law	3.0
1.	DI.1100/01	Nepalese Conservation Law	3.0
2.	DI.1100/02	International Conversation Law	3.0
		Total credits	15

8th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.
1.	Jr. 100/10	Eastern Legal Philosophy of Law and Justice	3.0
2.	DL. 1100/03	Environment Law	3.0
3.	Cvl. 1200/01	Family Law	3.0
4.	Cn.800/05	Nepalese Federalism	1.5
5.	Cmrl.1000/06	Commercial Arbitration	1.5
Optional subjects			
Criminal Law Stream			
5.	CrI. 400/06	Digital Forensic Science - 2	1.5
6.	CrI.400/07	Penology	1.5
Commercial Law Stream			
5.	Cmrl.1000/05	Insurance Law	1.5
6.	Cmrl.1000/06	Cooperatives Law	1.5
Constitutional Law Stream			
5.	Cn.800/06	Equity and Tort Law	1.5
6.	Cn.800/07	Electoral Law	1.5
Development Law Stream			
5.	DL.1100/04	Civil Aviation Law	1.5
6.	DL.1100/05	Energy Law	1.5
		Total credit	15.0

9th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.HRS
1.	Jr. 100/10	Land and Housing Law	3
2.	Jr.100/11	Agrarian Law	3
3.	Jr.100/12	Labor Law	3
4.	Intl.500/07	International Humanitarian Law	3
5.	DL.1100/06	Cyber Law	3
6.	Cl.300/07	Clinical: Legal Professionalism Development	1.5
Optional			
Criminal Law Stream			
7.	CrI.400/06	Law Against Organized Crime	1.5
8.	CrI.400/07	Fiscal Crime Law	1.5
Commercial Law Stream			
7.	Crml.1000/07	Intellectual Property Law	1.5
8.	Crml. 1000/08	Taxation Law	1.5
Constitutional Law Stream			
7.	Cn.800/08	Citizenship and Nationality Law	1.5
8.	Cn.800/09	Corruption Prevention Law	1.5
Development Law Stream			
7.	DL. 1100/07	Mining Law	1.5
8.	DL.1100/08	Civil Aviation	1.5
		Total credit	19.5

10th Semester

S.no	Course Log	Subjects	CR.HRS
1.	Jr. 100/13	Health and Hygiene Jurisprudence	1.5
2.	Cn.800/10	Local Governance Law	1.5
3.	DL.1100/09	Transportation Safety Law	1.5
4.	Intl. 500/07	Private International Law	1.5
5.	Cl.300/08	Clinical: Pre-trial, trial Advocacy and Appellate Advocacy	3
6.	Lr.800/03	Dissertation	3
Criminal Law Stream			
7.	CrI.400/08	Law Against Organized Crime:Part-II	3
8.	CrI.400/09	Fiscal Crime Law	1.5
Commercial Law Stream			
7.	Crml.1000/09	Excise Duty Law	1.5
8.	Crml. 1000/10	Custom Law	3
Constitution Law Stream			
7.	Cn.800/10	Consumer Protection	3
8.	Cn.800/06.2	Sport Law	1.5
Development Law Stream			
7.	DL. 1100/10	Mountaineering Law	1.5
8.	DL.1100/11	Tourism Law	3
		Total credit	16.5

Course for Bachelor in Public Administration and Management (BPAM), a joint program with Kathmandu University

Approved by the Academic Council dated August 29, 2023 (2080 Bhadra 12)

Background

Public sector is the foundation of the state governance since it captures people's aspirations, translates into the public policy, designs and delivers public services. Likewise, the private sector is the biggest contributor for the development of a country. The role of civil service is pivotal to fulfill the needs and aspirations of citizens in the changing socio-economic environment of Nepal. With the promulgation of the new constitution, foundation of new structure of governance as federal system has been envisioned to leverage decision making authorities at local level with optimum utilization of resources; and accelerate national development activities. It has also expanded the scope of private sector from bottom, the grassroots-level. In order to capitalize these activities, human resource is one of the key components for successful implementation of the provisions and spirit of the constitution to execute and achieve this vision. This role greatly demands higher level of competencies and commitments of civil servants for effective, efficient and equitable delivery of public services as well as to accelerate the private sector from the community level. The new dimension of the public administration has very thin border line since private companies are also used in public service delivery as well as public agencies need to adapt the business norms and efficiency while dealing with public goods. Therefore, the need of blended skills of both public and private sector in human resources is inevitable to have the effective, efficient and inclusive growth.

Aim of the Course

The MU collaborating with KU has developed a blended course for bachelor students named Bachelor of Public Administration and Management (BPAM) from its inception. The course aims to orient, socialize and sensitize with core values, functions and practices of public and business administration which is collectively called Public Management. The program is designed in such a way that it enhanced the balanced capability with knowledge, skill and wisdom. It is expected to enhance students' core competencies so that they can deliver quality service to their clients (people) with greater extent of professionalism, serving attitude and empathetic behavior.

Objective of the course

To develop competent human resource for public and private sector

To fulfill the gap of inclusiveness in the employment sector

To promote skillful hands for self-employment

Eligibility in the program

Students who have passed +2 or equivalent from any discipline with a minimum of CGPA 1.6 or 40 percent shall be eligible to apply for admission to the BPAM program followed by at least 40 percent score in the MUMAT run by the university.

Medium of instruction and examination shall be English and Nepali.

Course Structure

The duration of BPAM program is of four years (eight semesters). The total weightage of the program has 120 credit covering administrative sciences and management with 93 credit, specialization 15 credit, research practical 12 credit as given below.

Semester I <<18 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope*
1.	BPAM 100-01	Comprehensive English and Grammar	3.0	Basic Literatures, Comprehension, Grammar	Prose, Poetry, Story, General and Basic Grammar, Comprehension, Writing
2.	BPAM 100-02	Nepali- Language; Literature and Writing	3.0	नेपाली साहित्यिक अध्ययन, व्याकरण तथा व्यवसायिक लेखन	निवन्ध, जिवनी, बोध, व्याकरण, बुदा टिपोट, टिप्पणी लेखन, व्यवसायिक पत्र लेखन आदि
3.	BPAM 100-03	Foundation of Public Administration and Management	3.0	Theory,	Fundamentals, Theoretical Foundation and Basic Concepts History and Current Thinking of Administration and Management
4.	BPAM 100-04	Fundamentals of Organization Behaviour	3.0	Theory	Concept and meaning, Theories, Development and Changing Nature / practices in OB
5.	BPAM 100-05	Nepal: History, Society and	3.0	Know Your Country	History, Geography, Economy, Society and Civic Life of People

		People			in Nepal
6.	BPAM 100-06	Basic Economics	3.0	Theory	Fundamental concepts, principles, and aspects of Economics

Semester II <<18 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr. H	Nature	Content Scope
1.	BPAM 200-01	Logical and Critical Thinking	3.0	Logical Reasoning, Practical	Definition and importance of Logic, Basic Concept and Terminology, Scientific Knowledge and Common Sense, Types of Logic, Buddhist Logic and Truth, Islamic System of Logic, Critical Thinking approach, Ambedkar's Critical Thinking, Critical Race Theory
2.	BPAM 200-02	Foundation of Social Sciences	3.0	Theory	Social Sciences: Concept and meaning of Social Science, Scope of Social Science and its implication in Governance and Management
3.	BPAM 200-03	Fundamentals of Governance	3.0	Theory, and application	Governance: concept and Meaning Public and Corporate governance
4.	BPAM 200-04	Macro Economics	3.0	Theory and application	Fundamentals of macro-economics, application
5.	BPAM 200-05	Development Administration	3.0	Theory and application	Development Administration as specialized governance study, theories and tools of action, application
6.	BPAM 200-06	Sociology and Sociological Thoughts	3.0	Theory and application	Fundamental concept of sociology as science of society, Sociological Theories, Different schools of thoughts

Semester III <<15 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
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1.	BPAM 300-01	ICT and Computer Application	3.0	Applied Skill Development	ITC, E-governance, Computer Application
2.	BPAM 300-02	Mathematics for Economics and Management	3.0	Applied Study	Applied mathematics to understand economics and business management. Mathematical concepts and models/applications
3.	BPAM 300-03	Public Finance Fundamentals	3.0	Theory, and application	Fundamentals of public finance, concepts and approaches, application
4.	BPAM 300-04	Project Planning and Management	3.0	Theory and application	Fundamentals of public sector project planning and management, application
5.	BPAM 300-05	ICT, Computer Application and e- governance-Project work	1.5	Practical application	Office attachment, concept development, modeling and project report
6.	BPAM 300-06	Project appraisal and development practical	1.5	Practical application	Project attachment, concept for new project, appraisal and project planning-Guided practical assignment

Semester IV <<15 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
1.	BPAM 400-01	Caste, Class, Gender, Ethnicity and Exclusion	3.0	Theory and application	Evolution of Social Stratification; Caste, Class, Gender, Ethnicity and Structural Exclusion, Theoretical debate on exclusion, Cost of exclusion, Nepalese perspective.
2.	BPAM 400-02	Climate & Disaster Risk Governance	3.0	Theory and application	Concept of climate change and disaster risk, risk governance, system and process
3.	BPAM 400-03	Applied Statistics for public management	3.0	Theory and application	Use of statistics in public management and its practices.
4.	BPAM 400-04	Multi-level Governance in Federal System	3.0	Theory and context understanding	Provision and Practices, International Context, Nepalese Context
5.	BPAM 400-05	NGO, Civil Society and Local Governance	3.0	Theory and context understanding	Role of NGOs, Civil Society in service delivery, use of civil societies by local governments and its implication

Semester V <<18 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
	BPAM 500-01	Provincial and Local Governance	3.0	Constitutional Provisions and Practices	Functional mandate, Governance practices in the field
1.	BPAM 500-02	Fiscal Interrelationship in Federal System of Nepal (IGF)	3.0	Theory and context understanding	Fiscal Federalism and Fiscal Interrelationship in Federal Nepal
2.	BPAM 500-03	Public Administration in Comparative Perspectives	3.0	Theory, and application	Public Administration applied in multi-lateral organizations
3.	BPAM 500-04	Entrepreneurship and Innovations— in public and business context	3.0	Theory and application	Concept and approaches of Entrepreneurship and Innovations, Regulatory Provisions of public or private entities, Internship (2 Month)
4.	BPAM 500-05	Research Methodology-I	3.0	Theory and application	Fundamentals of Research, Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed methods of research, Design and Research execution
5.	BPAM 500-06	Write-shops and paper writing	3 (1+2)	Practical	How to write journal articles, research papers for publishing? Thematic research paper writing (2 papers)—public administration, governance, management themes.

Semester VI (Specialization through electives)

Public Administration Stream <<15 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
1.	BPAM 600-01	Basics of Public Policy	3.0	Theory and application	Concept of public policy, Policy Thoughts, Designing and implementation of Public Policy
2.	BPAM 600-02	Development Planning and Management	3.0	Theory and application	Planning needs and process, Formulation plan and its implementation. Bottlenecks of planning
3.	BPAM 600-03	Planning and Budgeting at sub-national level (include GRB)	3.0	Theory and application	Concept of budgeting, interlinkage of planning and budgeting, Planning process in Province Government, Planning process in Local Government.

4.	BPAM 600-04	Designing and Delivering Public Services	3.0		Theory and practical application	Principles of public services, Design principles and components, Design workshop, public service assessment, preparation and presentation of innovation in service.
5.	BPAM 600-05	Climate Change Adaptation and Management	3.0		Theory and application	Climate accounting and financing, Green growth development, Green-entrepreneurship, Government role, Role of public

Management Stream <<15 credit>>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
1.	BPAM 600-06	Corporate Governance	3.0	Theory and practical application	Theory and Concept of Corporate Governance; Societal, cultural and environmental aspects of Corporate Governance; Accountability, Ethics and Social Responsibility
2.	BPAM 600-07	Advancing in Human Resource Management	3.0	Theory and application	Concept and definition, Workforce diversity and its management, Recruitment, Selection and Placement, Continued Capacity building
3.	BPAM 600-08	Financial (Corporate and Public) Management	3.0	Theory and application	Concept of Corporate finance and Public Finance, Financial Policy (Global and National), Financial system in Federal Structure, Financial forecasting and budgeting
4.	BPAM 600-09	Operations Management	3.0	Theory and application	Concept of Operations Management, Importance and approaches
5.	BPAM 600-11	Procurement Management	3.0	Theory and application	Concept, importance, approaches and Regulatory provisions of Procurement Management, Inventory and Efficient use of Goods/Services, Challenges of Procurement

Semester VII <<11 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
		Gender and Social Inclusion Studies	3.0	Applied Study	Sexuality, Gender and Social Inclusion; Issues of gender, ethnicity and caste and diversity management Gender and SI in Nepalese Perspective (Legal

					Provisions and its implications)
1.	BPAM 700-01	Research Methodology-III	3 (2+1)	Practical Application	Proposal design workshops, questionnaire and other tools design exercises [2 credit, general] Methodology seminar [Stream Focus, Facilitated by theme- expert]
2.	BPAM 700-02	Developing research proposal & workshop	6.0	Practical	Proposal for proposed thesis research development, progress sharing and contestation

Semester VIII <<12 credit >>

SN	Course Log	Subjects	Cr.	Nature	Content Scope
1.	BPAM 800-01	Thesis writing	9.0	Research	Topic selected by the student relevant with the course and approved by the concerned faculty. Final Approval by the Research Committee.
		Presentation and Dissemination conference		Viva-voce	As specified by Research Committee Dissemination conference not compulsory

STUDENT CODE OF CONDUCT

Madhesh University Organization and Educational Administration Rules, 2079 has spelled out the provision of Student Code of Conduct in rule 161 as follows.

- (1) In order to fully comply with and assist in fully complying with the acts, rules and guidelines of the University, the students of the University shall follow the following conduct:
 - (a) To participate diligently and honestly in the educational program.
 - (b) To develop mutual cooperation and goodwill among students, faculties, employees and officials.
 - (c) To follow the conduct prescribed by the Executive Council.
 - (d) To be engrossed for academic advancement.
 - (e) Do not act contrary to the goal and interest of the University.

- (2) A student who violates the Code of Conduct mentioned in Sub-rule (1) may be punished by the faculty head as follows. (a) warning, (b) giving written alert, (c) suspending from classes for a maximum of 15 days, (d) expelling from the university or affiliated colleges for a specified period of time, (e) prohibiting entry into future educational programs for a specified period of time.
- (3) If he has to be expelled from studying in the University for a certain period of time the Executive Council may, on the recommendation of the faculty head, expel such student.
- (4) A student who has been punished under this rule may appeal to the Registrar within seven days from the date of receiving such punishment.
- (5) If the Registrar upholds the punishment as per the Sub-rule (4), the punished student may appeal to the University Appellate Commission within 15 days from the date of receipt of such notice.
- (6) According to this rule, the application filed with the Appellate Commission has to be finalized within 30 days of the filing of the appeal.
- (7) The procedure relating to the hearing of appeals shall be prescribed by the Commission.

Currently, we have our Dean who is leading Academic Development and he has research Expertise and we are open for research collaboration. Brief publication list of Dean

- Guided M.Sc. students in thesis development, contributing to the publication: Research Report - 2022 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030334>).
- Prepared a comprehensive research report on the strategic development plan for Nepal's first technological university: *Strategic Proposal for Developing Madan Bhandari Technological University* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7316861>).
- Conducted a study and authored the *Initial University Conception Report and Curriculum Development Report* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030326>).
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LIST OF PUBLISHED PAPERS IN JOURNALS

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Seminar & Publications

- [1] 7th ORSN Webinar Speaker on Status of Casual Worker in Nepal https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vtnTmprX_0Y&t=97s
- [2] Addressed 6 international conference as keynote speaker in physical conference and 1 as chief guest and presented in 34 international conferences
- [3] Anjay Kumar Mishra: Factors affecting and Performance Assessment of ongoing Construction projects under Town Development Fund, Nepal Presented in: The 11th Triennial Conference of Association of Asia Pacific Operational Research Societies (APORS 2018, AUGUST 6-9) At: Radisson Hotel, Kathmandu
- [4] Anjay Kumar Mishra: Implication of theory of Constraints in Project Management, Presented in: 6TH Uniglobe International Management Conference, Kathmandu, Nepal
- [5] Keynote Speaker at FDP on Climate Change, Env. Sustainability & Entrepreneurship by Kabul University, Afghanistan and SAIARD at <https://youtu.be/D4f3umjsnWk>
- [6] Keynote Speaker at Logistics and Shipping Management webinar was conducted through a virtual platform from the 21st August to 23rd August by AMET University in collaboration with Tamilnadu Advanced Technical Training Institute (TATTI) available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TxlMufKkN1I&t=631s>
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- [10] Keynote speech and Session Chair: Mishra, A. (2024, June 17). Embracing Green Technology for a Sustainable Future through Talent Management. International Conference on Green Technology and Talent Management, Nepal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11966459>
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- [14] Keynote speech: Mishra, A. K. (2024, April 7). Harmony in Innovation: Navigating Global Business Landscapes through Emerging Technologies and Dynamic Management Strategies. Conference: 4th annual International Conference on "Harmony in Innovation: Navigating Global Business Landscapes through Emerging Technologies and Dynamic Management Strategies," hosted by Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune in collaboration with EMAA Business School, Morocco; The Centre of Economic Diplomacy, Croatia, Europe; Dr. Soetomo University, Indonesia; Boston International College, Nepal; Jansons School of Business, Coimbatore, India; Association of Indian Management Schools, India; and Center for Education Growth & Research, India., India. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10937592>

Editorial

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